

CheckMyName Service Description

David Fichtmueller (FUB-BGBM)
Walter G. Berendsohn (FUB-BGBM)
Anton Güntsch (FUB-BGBM)

Freie Universität Berlin - Botanic Garden and Botanical Museum Berlin (FUB-BGBM)

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Content

Introduction	3
User interface	3
Caveats.....	5
Underlying data	5
Descriptors for taxonomic datasets.....	6
Descriptors for name matching services.....	7
Descriptors for dataset-in-service combinations.....	7
Mapping of user-interface selections to table-attributes.....	8
Data input and processing.....	10
Acknowledgements and author contributions	10

Document history:

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes
0.1	19.9.2025	W.G. Berendsohn	Initial draft
1.0	10.12.2025	D. Fichtmueller	Document formatting and revisions
1.1	19.12.2025	W.G. Berendsohn, D. Fichtmueller	Minor adjustments and revisions

Document: Documentation

Version: 1.1

Date: 2025-12-19

Introduction

CheckMyName is a web tool that allows users to find suitable service and dataset combinations for taxonomic name matching. It offers a simple user interface where users can input their requirements which will automatically filter the list of available services with the corresponding taxonomic datasets against which the name can be checked.

The tool can be found at: <https://cetaf-eu.github.io/CheckMyName/>.

Its source code repository is <https://github.com/CETAF-EU/CheckMyName>.

User interface

The user interface of the prototype for selecting the suitable name matching services is a relatively simple filtered search page with a details panel for a single selected record. By default, all of the taxonomic dataset/name-matching service combinations are listed on the page, giving a brief overview of the service, the dataset and their most important features (Fig. 1). The user can then use filters as described above to reduce the number of results presented (Fig. 2). All of the filtering is done via JavaScript in the browser, so no dedicated backend search infrastructure is needed.

Check My Name
Taxonomic Name Matching Service Explorer

Using scientific names based on globally recognized rules of biological nomenclature enables precise and effective communication about the living world. One goal of the TETTRIs project is to integrate taxonomic resources to support cross-domain data linkage. A key requirement for this is the ability to connect names across different sources (particularly with taxonomic data aggregators), which relies on name-matching. This prototype tool helps biodiversity data curators identify name-matching services suited to their specific needs.

Filters

- ▶ Geographic Scope
- ▶ Taxonomic Scope
- ▶ Number of records
- ▶ Purpose
- ▶ Data Linkage
- ▶ Technical Requirements

Suitable Matching Services and Datasets (56)

ChecklistBank Name Match Catalogue of Life	Algae Animalia Bacteria Cyanobacteria Fungi Plantae Virus	Direct Matching Interface File Matching Interface Download Full From Website Download Dataset API Local Installation	Canonical Name Checked Full Name Checked Acceptance Classification	●
ChecklistBank Name Match Catalogue of Life eXtended Release	Algae Animalia Bacteria Cyanobacteria Fungi Plantae Virus	Direct Matching Interface File Matching Interface Download Full From Website Download Dataset API Local Installation	Canonical Name Checked Full Name Checked Classification	●
GBIF Species Matcher GBIF Backbone Taxonomy (2023)	Algae Animalia Bacteria Cyanobacteria Fungi Plantae Virus	File Matching Interface Download Full From Website API	Canonical Name Checked	●
WFO Plant List World Flora Online Plant List	Plantae	Direct Matching Interface File Matching Interface OpenRefine Reconciliation Interface Download Full From Website Download Dataset API Local Installation	Canonical Name Checked Full Name Checked Classification	●

Fig 1: The user interface for the dataset/service selection

Filters

Geographic Scope

- Global
- Europe
 - Austria
 - Belgium
 - Bulgaria
 - Croatia
 - Cyprus
 - Czech Republic
 - Denmark

Taxonomic Scope

- Multiple or unknown
- Animals
- Plants
- Algae
- Fungi
- Bluegreen algae
- Bacteria
- Virus
- Include fossils

Number of records

Number of names to be check simultaneously:

In the User Interface (add items via copy & paste)

less or equal 5000

more than 5000

Via file upload

less or equal 5000

more than 5000

Purpose

I want to check ...

- Orthography of canonical name (name without author / year)
- Orthography of full name (also checking author abbreviations and year)
- Acceptance (if it is a taxon name, or a synonym of another name, or taxonomically unresolved)
- Classification (inclusion in higher taxa according to the dataset's hierarchy)

Data Linkage

Technical Requirements

Suitable Matching Services and Datasets (10)

ChecklistBank Name	Algae	Animalia	Bacteria	Cyanobacteria	Fungi	Direct Matching Interface	File Matching Interface	Canonical Name Checked
Match	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Catalogue of Life	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Fig. 2: The current user interface with some filters applied, reducing the number of results.

When the user clicks on one of the list entries, a more detailed page will open up, to show all of the information about the dataset/service combination (Fig. 3).

- Name Checked 🇩🇪

Checked Acceptance
- Name Checked 🌐

Classification
- Name Checked 🇸🇪

Checked Acceptance
- Name Checked 🌐

Checked Acceptance
- Name Checked 🌐

Checked Acceptance

ChecklistBank Name Match ✕

with **Artsdatabanken (Norway) / Nortaxa** dataset

CLB dataset 2030 [12 jul 2025]

Geographic Scope 🇳🇴 Norway

Taxonomic Scope Algae Animalia Cyanobacteria Fungi Plantae

Features Direct Matching Interface File Matching Interface
Download Full From Website API Local Installation

Website of the Dataset <https://artsdatabanken.no/>

API Documentation <https://nortaxa.artsdatabanken.no/swagger/index.html>

Fig. 3: The current details view for a specific dataset/service combination

Caveats

The implementation is a demonstrator. The following caveats have been identified in the implementation as of November 2025:

- A button to reset all filters is missing
- Details view to include more data and structure of the display to be revised
- Some errors and pending additions to the data tables have to be implemented.
- Geographic scope currently restricted to EU member states.
- A procedure to update the underlying data tables in a seamless way has to be defined.

Underlying data

The data schema (Fig. 4) consists of three tables describing datasets, services, and the combination of dataset and service, respectively.

Fig. 4: Relational data structure

For user queries, the 3 data tables (datasets, services, dataset-in-service) will be denormalized (in the process, automatic filling of geographic areas and taxonomic groups will be carried out where general terms have been defined) and exported into a JSON file, which is then used by the user interface to display the services.

Descriptors for taxonomic datasets

Parameters of importance for the user's selection of a name matching workflow were recorded for 34 datasets that can be used in name matching services.

Field Name	Data Type	Description (Optional)
dataset_internal_id	Number	An (internal) ID for the dataset record
short_title	Short Text	Short title
display_title	Short Text	Long title
dataset_description_uri	Short Text	A description given by the site providing the web interface
versioning	Short Text	Description of release policies
marine_only	Yes/No	Focus (almost entirely) on marine organisms
fossil_only	Yes/No	Focus on (almost entirely) fossil organisms
contains_fossils	Yes/No	Includes fossil names
stable_name_id	Yes/No	Stability of name ID is presumed (or stated in a policy)
stable_id_attribute_name	Short Text	Name of the attribute of the ID as output in exports / web interface
stable_id_policy_stated	Short Text	Normally a URL describing the ID policy
stable_id_caveats_and_notes	Long Text	Problems or features noted with respect to the IDs
name_id_resolved_2_name	Yes/No	Name_ID can be included in URI, leads to a name page (independent of its status)
name_id_resolved_2_taxon	Yes/No	Name_ID can be included in URI, leads to a taxon page where the name is found (as taxon or syn)
download_full_from_website	Yes/No	Checklist data, i.e. ID(s), name, name elements and status, not necessarily also associated data
download_partial_from_webs	Yes/No	Checklist data
download_website_uri	Short Text	Download website
download_formats	Short Text	Checklist data
homepage_uri	Short Text	URI of general website of the specific dataset
query_uri	Short Text	URI of web query form for the specific dataset
access_open	Yes/No	Including -by, -sa and -nc clauses
License	Short Text	E.g. CC-by; see access_uri for access policy statement
access_conditions_uri	Short Text	A web page detailing conditions for access
has_api	Yes/No	An application programming interface is present
api_documentation	Short Text	Documentation for the application programming interface
biota	Yes/No	Taxonomic scope includes all organisms (should automatically include all individual scopes)
algae	Yes/No	Taxonomic scope includes eucaryotic algae
animalia	Yes/No	Taxonomic scope includes animals
bacteria	Yes/No	Taxonomic scope includes bacteria
cyanobacteria	Yes/No	Taxonomic scope includes cyanobacteria (blue-green algae)
fungi	Yes/No	Taxonomic scope includes fungi (including lichenes)
plantae	Yes/No	Taxonomic scope includes plants (always vascular plants, may or may not include "bryophytes")
virus	Yes/No	Taxonomic scope includes virus
global	Yes/No	Geographic scope is global (should automatically include all individual scopes)
europe	Yes/No	Geographic scope includes Europe (should automatically include all individual countries)
austria	Yes/No	
belgium	Yes/No	
bulgaria	Yes/No	

Table 1: Structure of the table describing taxonomic datasets

Descriptors for name matching services

Parameters of importance for the user's selection of a name matching workflow were recorded for 18 name matching services.

The structure of the table is given in Table 2.

Field Name	Data Type	Description (Optional)
service_ID	Number	Internal ID (primary key)
service_name	Short Text	Short name of the service
service_organisation	Short Text	The organisation or institution supporting the service
service_description_uri	Short Text	A link to details about the service
test	Short Text	Test result notes
direct_matching_interface	Yes/No	Names can be directly input on the website (no file upload required)
direct_matching_URI	Short Text	Link to the matching web interface
direct_matching_restriction	Number	Limit of records that can be directly matched
direct_matching_interactive	Yes/No	Users can manually match their unmatched records with offered fuzzy matches
file_matching_interface	Yes/No	File upload for matching possible
file_matching_uri	Short Text	The web interface for file upload
file_matching_restriction	Number	Limit of records that can be uploaded for matching
file_upload_format(s)	Short Text	Format of name-containing file that can be uploaded
file_upload_name_elements	Short Text	Allow input of name components in separate fields in uploads (e.g. genus, epithets, author(s) e
process_ignore_terms	Short Text	(optional or standard) Initial processing of name can filter out terms for uncertainty (c., cf., aff.,
process_nomenclatural_code	Short Text	Duplicate names governed by different codes may be correctly matched when the code is indica
output_includes_input_column	Yes/No	Matching result is united with uploaded records (particularly important for local ID)
output_includes_candidates	Short Text	Exact matches and fuzzy matches are returned in one file or two separate files
output_includes_dataset_record	Short Text	The identifier given in the source dataset is returned
output_file_formats	Short Text	Format of the output file
matching_process_description	Short Text	Description of the matching process
matching_process_parameters	Short Text	User can select, e.g., fuzzy matching
api_public_access	Yes/No	API for external users available (may require permission)
api_documentation_uri	Short Text	API textual documentation
api_endpoint_uri	Short Text	API access point
R-package	Yes/No	An R-package is provided for name matching (incl. data)
open_refine_reconciliation_if	Yes/No	OpenRefine reconciliation interface available
open_refine_reconciliation_if	Short Text	OpenRefine reconciliation interface access point
open_refine_documentation	Short Text	How to use for OpenRefine reconciliation interface
local_installation	Yes/No	Entire service can be downloaded and installed locally

Table 2: Structure of the table describing name matching services

Descriptors for dataset-in-service combinations

Parameters of importance for the user's selection of a name matching workflow were recorded for 57 combinations of dataset and name matching service. The structure of the table is given in Table 3.

Field Name	Data Type	Description (Optional)
ID	AutoNumber	
dataset_fk	Number	Dataset ID
service_fk	Number	Service ID
caveats	Short Text	Potential problems in the linkage
notes	Short Text	Notes
full_name_checked	Yes/No	False if only canonical name check
output_taxonomic_status	Yes/No	Taxonomic status (e.g. accepted / synonym / unresolved) is included in output
output_nomenclatural_status	Yes/No	Nomenclatural status is included in output
output_classification	Yes/No	Classification (higher taxon, accepted taxon) is included in the output
output_persistent_id	Yes/No	Service provides a persistent identifier for the records in the dataset
output_persistent_resolvable	Yes/No	Service provides a persistent resolvable identifier (may resolve to the source or to the service provider)
download_dataset	Yes/No	Dataset can be downloaded from service site

Table 3: Structure of the table describing dataset/service combinations

Mapping of user-interface selections to table-attributes.

Organism group (choose multiple or one or several of the following; mark fossil / marine)

	Attribute	Type	Notes
Multiple or unknown	datasets.biota	boolean	(marks the following 7 groups upon matrix input)
Animals	datasets.animalia	boolean	
Plants	datasets.plantae	boolean	
Algae	datasets.algae	boolean	
Fungi	datasets.fungi	boolean	
Bluegreen algae	datasets.cyanobacteria	boolean	
Bacteria	datasets.bacteria	boolean	
Viruses	datasets.virus	boolean	
Include fossils	datasets.contains_fossils	boolean	
Only fossils	datasets.fossile_only	boolean	
Only marine species	datasets.marine_only	boolean	

Geographic scope (choose Global, Europe, or one to several countries)

	Attribute	Type	Notes
Global	datasets.global	boolean	(marks all the following upon input)
Europe	datasets.europe	boolean	marks all countries upon input
[country name]	datasets.[country name]	boolean	upon input replaced by country code (ISO 3166-1 alpha-2)

Countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Republic of Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom

Data size (Number of names to be checked simultaneously)

	Attribute	Type	Notes
.. cut and paste IF	services.direct_matching_restriction	numeric	useful classes: < 5000, >=5000
.. file upload	services.file_matching_restriction	numeric	useful classes: < 5000, >=5000

Purpose of name matching (I want to check ... - choose at least one)

	Attribute	Type	Notes
orthography of canonical name (name without author / year)	*		covered by all datasets

Orthography of full name (also checking author abbreviations and year)	dataset_in_service.full_name_checked	boolean	
Acceptance (if its a taxon name, or a synonym of another name, or taxonomically unresolved)	dataset_in_service.output_taxonomic_status	boolean	
Classification (inclusion in higher taxa according to the dataset's hierarchy)	dataset_in_service.output_classification	boolean	

Data linkage requirements (choose one)

	Attribute	Type	Notes
I am not interested in identifiers and links for the name	*		
I want a persistent identifier for the name in the dataset that corresponds to my local name	dataset_in_service.output_persistent_id	boolean	
I want a persistent resolvable identifier for the name in the dataset that corresponds to my local name	dataset_in_service.output_persistent_resolvable_id	boolean	
I want a persistent resolvable identifier for the taxon (accepted name) that corresponds to my local name	dataset.name_id_resolved_2_taxon	boolean	

Technical requirement (choose any)

I want to	Attribute	Type	Notes
write or paste the names into a web interface (usually limited number)	services.direct_matching_interface	boolean	(may include file pasting)
upload a list or table and receive the result as table or tables	services.file_matching_interface	boolean	
use OpenRefine as the name matching tool	services.open_refine_reconciliation_if	boolean	
download the data, I'll do the matching in my own database	datasets.download_full_from_website OR dataset_in_service.download_dataset	boolean, boolean	

program my name matching using the on-line API of the aggregator	services.api_public_access	boolean	(available, may need permission or login)
use an R-package that can be downloaded	services.R_package	boolean	(documentation: field for API-documentation)
install the name matching service on my server	services.local_installation	boolean	(usually a Docker package)

Data input and processing

For data input, the database with the tables detailed above was implemented using Microsoft Access 2024. It can be downloaded at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17986699>.

In order to make the data useable by the website, some processing was required. The data was exported from the Access database and uploaded to an online spreadsheet software. A Jupyter Notebook could then access the data, process and reformat it before writing it in the JSON file used by the web application. The notebook can be found in the *processing* directory in the Github repository. We are aware that this workflow still has room for optimisation and improvement.

Acknowledgements and author contributions

The TETTRIs project (Transforming European Taxonomy through Training, Research and Innovations, <https://tettris.eu/>) is a contribution of the taxonomic community gathered around CETAF, the Consortium of European taxonomic facilities, to provide knowledge, systems and services to tackle biodiversity loss.

TETTRIs was carried out with the financial support of the European Union (Grant Agreement 101081903).

The work presented here was carried out under TETTRIs Work Package 2 under the direction of Anton Güntsch, with Walter Berendsohn contributing the idea and the cataloguing of the relevant services and datasets and David Fichtmüller the implementation of the web interface. All authors discussed and revised the document.

We gratefully acknowledge the contribution of the reviewers of the original (unpublished) work package deliverable, Sofie Meeus and Olaf Bánki.